

Development of an Intelligent Agent for Knowledge Extraction in the Pathogens in Foods (PIF) Database with Machine Learning

Lucas Ribeiro Silva

Dissertation presented to the School of Technology and Management of Bragança to obtain the master's degree in Informatics within the scope of the double degree program with the Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais

Supervisors:

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Dedication

For my mother, Maria Aparecida Ribeiro Silva, and in loving memory of my father, João Limério da Silva. Thank you for your unwavering support, belief in me, and unconditional love. To my family, friends, and beloved pets, thank you for the love and for making this long journey so much more enjoyable. Finally, with my deepest gratitude to my advisors and with a special thanks to PIF's head researcher Úrsula Gonzales-Barron for her invaluable leadership.

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Abstract

Scientific databases like the Pathogens in Foods (PIF) Database hold valuable public health data but are often inaccessible to experts lacking programming skills. This research addresses this gap by developing and evaluating a novel Visual Natural Language Interface (V-NLI) for the PIF database. The resulting PIF Intelligent Agent empowers users to perform complex queries, conduct meta-analyses, and generate dynamic reports using natural language. The agent uses a hybrid, dual-mode architecture separating language interpretation from statistical computation. An "Open Chat Mode" offers a flexible exploratory interface via a tool-calling Small Language Model (SLM) with Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG). A "Guided Meta-Analysis Mode" provides a structured workflow for generating reproducible scientific reports through a dedicated R-server backend. A comprehensive evaluation benchmarked five SLMs: Phi-4 Mini (3.8B), MFDoom/deepseek-r1-tool-calling (14B), Cogito (14B), Qwen 3 (8B), and Gemini 2.5 Pro. While all models achieved flawless functional accuracy, their effectiveness was determined by interpretive quality. The ability to generate concise, factually coherent text was the key differentiator, with smaller, instruction-tuned models showing performance comparable or superior in conciseness to larger models. The end-to-end system proved highly reliable, validating the architecture and establishing interpretive fidelity as a critical benchmark for domain-specific agents.

Keywords: Natural Language Interface, Small Language Models, Food Safety, Meta-Analysis, Data Visualization, Tool-Using Agents.

Resumo

Bases de dados científicas, como a Pathogens in Foods (PIF) Database, contêm dados valiosos para a saúde pública, mas são muitas vezes inacessíveis a especialistas sem competências de programação. Esta investigação reduz essa lacuna ao desenvolver e avaliar uma nova Interface Visual de Linguagem Natural (V-NLI) para a base PIF. O Agente Inteligente PIF permite realizar consultas complexas, conduzir meta-análises e gerar relatórios dinâmicos em linguagem natural. O agente adota uma arquitetura híbrida, em modo duplo, separando a interpretação da linguagem do cálculo estatístico. Um “Modo de Chat Aberto” oferece uma interface exploratória flexível com um Small Language Model (SLM) e Geração Aumentada por Recuperação (RAG). Um “Modo Guiado de Meta-Análise” disponibiliza um fluxo estruturado para relatórios científicos reprodutíveis via backend dedicado em R-server. Uma avaliação abrangente comparou cinco SLMs: Phi-4 Mini (3,8B), MFDoom/de-epseek-r1-tool-calling (14B), Cogito (14B), Qwen 3 (8B) e Gemini 2.5 Pro. Embora todos os modelos tenham atingido precisão funcional impecável, a eficácia foi determinada pela qualidade interpretativa. A capacidade de gerar texto conciso e factualmente coerente foi o principal diferenciador, com modelos menores, afinados por instruções, a exibirem concisão comparável ou superior face a modelos maiores. O sistema fim-a-fim mostrou-se altamente fiável, validando a arquitetura e afirmando a fidelidade interpretativa como critério crucial para agentes específicos de domínio.

Palavras-chave: Interface de Linguagem Natural, Small Language Models, Segurança Alimentar, Meta-Análise, Visualização de Dados, Agentes com Utilização de Ferramentas.

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Acronyms

AC Analytical Consistency. 49–52, 56, 65, 66, 70

AI Artificial Intelligence. 2, 4, 9, 14

ANN Approximate Nearest Neighbor. 20

API Application Programming Interface. 11

ATN Augmented Transition Network. 6

CCG Combinatory Categorical Grammar. 8

CoT Chain-of-Thought. 15

DI Data Integrity. 49, 51, 53, 66, 67, 70

EEF1 Entity Extraction F1-score. 49, 51, 53, 66, 67, 70

FAISS Facebook AI Similarity Search. 20

ICA Intent Classification Accuracy. 49, 51, 53, 66, 67, 70

ICL In-Context learning. 14, 16

IQC Interpretation Quality and Coherence. xii, 50–54, 63, 65, 66, 70

LLM Large Language Model. 9, 11, 14, 16, 17, 19, 51

LoRA Low-Rank Adaptation. 13

LSTM Long Short-Term Memory. 10

SQL MongoDB Query Language. 2

NLI Natural Language Interface. 2, 3, 23

NLIDB Natural Language Interface for Database. 4–8, 20–22, 24

NLP Natural Language Processing. 2, 3, 8–10, 14, 67, 70, 71

NLU Natural Language Understanding. 3, 23, 27, 32, 40, 47

PEFT Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning. 13

PIF Pathogens in Foods. xii, 1–5, 10, 12, 16, 20–23, 25, 26, 28, 29, 32, 34, 42, 44, 47, 49, 67, 69, 71, 72

RAG Retrieval-Augmented Generation. 2–5, 16–21, 23, 26–28, 34, 44

RNN Recurrent Neural Network. 9, 10

RQI Report Quality Index. xii, 52, 65–67, 70

Seq2Seq Sequence-to-Sequence. 8, 22

SLM Small Language Model. xii, 2–5, 9, 11, 12, 16, 19, 22, 23, 25–27, 29, 32, 39–42, 44–51, 53, 54, 63, 65–67, 69–71

SLMPI Small Language Model Performance Index. 51, 70

SQL Structured Query Language. 6–9

V-NLI Visualization-Oriented Natural Language Interface. x, 3, 5, 21–24, 67, 69, 70

VI Visual Informativeness. xii, 51, 52, 57, 58, 65

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and Motivation

Ensuring food safety is a critical global concern, as foodborne illnesses continue to pose significant threats to public health and economic stability. According to the World Health Organization, an estimated 600 million people—almost 1 in 10 worldwide—fall ill after consuming contaminated food each year, resulting in 420,000 deaths. Children under five years of age bear 40% of the global foodborne disease burden, accounting for 125,000 deaths annually. From an economic standpoint, unsafe food leads to annual productivity losses and medical expenses of around US\$ 110 billion in low- and middle-income countries alone [1]. These figures underscore the urgency of developing robust surveillance systems, data infrastructures, and analytical tools that can support timely and evidence-based decision-making in food safety.

The PIF database represents an important step in this direction. With over 13,100 curated entries, it catalogues the occurrence and concentration of pathogenic bacteria, viruses, protozoa, and nematodes in foodstuffs, primarily across Europe. Covering the entire farm-to-fork chain, it provides a structured and harmonized knowledge base for food safety agencies, risk assessors, and researchers [2]. However, despite its value, leveraging

the PIF database effectively is not trivial. Querying its contents requires technical proficiency in MongoDB Query Language (MQL), a skill set that many domain experts—such as microbiologists, epidemiologists, and public health officials—may lack. For instance, a microbiologist wishing to identify the food categories most frequently contaminated with *Listeria monocytogenes* might find it difficult to construct the necessary queries or interpret raw tabular outputs.

Moreover, the heterogeneity and volume of data introduce additional barriers. Extracting meaningful insights often involves navigating complex schemas, reconciling variable reporting formats, and conducting meta-analyses that are both time-consuming and prone to error. This is particularly problematic in the context of food safety, where timely and accurate information is crucial for decision-making and policy formulation [3]. This creates what can be described as a knowledge access gap, where vast amounts of structured data remain underutilized due to technical entry barriers [4]. The problem is not exclusive to food safety—similar issues are seen across domains that rely on large scientific datasets—but the high stakes of foodborne outbreaks make it particularly critical here.

To bridge this gap, Natural Language Interfaces (NLIs) and intelligent agents are gaining traction. By allowing users to interact with databases through conversational language rather than rigid query syntax, these systems lower the technical threshold for data access. Combined with advances in machine learning, Natural Language Processing (NLP), and visualization, NLIs enable non-technical experts to focus on interpretation and decision-making rather than data manipulation and query formulation [5]. Recent developments in SLM and Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) provide additional opportunities: lightweight models can be deployed efficiently, while RAG methods ensure that answers remain grounded in the actual database content rather than relying on the model’s internal knowledge [6], [7], [8]. In food safety, these approaches are consistent with the broader trend of applying Artificial Intelligence (AI) to tasks such as rapid pathogen detection, predictive risk assessment, and surveillance analytics [9].

1.2 Objectives and Research Questions

The main objective of this thesis is to develop an intelligent agent for the PIF database in the form of a V-NLI. This system is conceived as a chatbot platform that enables domain experts to formulate natural language queries, conduct meta-analyses, generate dynamic reports, and visualize compiled data. By integrating multiple components—embedding models, SLM, prompt engineering techniques, vector search, and meta-analyses pipelines—the V-NLI seeks to make pathogen surveillance data both more accessible and more actionable.

1.2.1 Specific Objectives

1. Evaluate and compare SLMs for Natural Language Understanding (NLU).
2. Design and implement a V-NLI for the PIF database.
3. Integrate visualization and reporting capabilities, including meta-analysis workflows.

1.2.2 Research Questions

The research is guided by three primary research questions:

1. **RQ1:** How can NLP and machine learning be leveraged to design an intelligent agent for the PIF database?
2. **RQ2:** What SLMs are most effective in this domain?
3. **RQ3:** How can the system support meta-analyses, dynamic reporting, and visualization for non-technical users?

This research aims to make several key contributions. It will extend the state of the art in NLIs for specialized scientific databases by tailoring modern NLP and RAG architectures to food safety data. A central part of this work will involve an empirical

evaluation of different SLMs to determine their effectiveness in this domain, with a focus on comparing the quality and coherence of their generated interpretations. The thesis will also present a novel multi-server architecture that integrates natural language interaction with statistical meta-analysis and visualization. Ultimately, this work seeks to deliver a practical tool for the food safety community, demonstrating how lightweight AI systems can be built for critical public health applications while lowering technical barriers to data access and analysis.

1.3 Scope and Dissertation Structure

This work is scoped to the PIF database and its schema, focusing on foodborne bacteria, viruses, and protozoa. Natural language capabilities are domain-specific and not designed for general-purpose querying without adaptation. The meta-analysis module supports selected models (e.g., prevalence estimation, trend analysis, comparisons by food category or geography) chosen in consultation with food safety experts. The system prioritizes computational efficiency by using SLMs, at the cost of reduced flexibility in handling highly diverse queries.

The remainder of this dissertation is organized as follows. Chapter 2 reviews the theoretical foundations and related literature, covering the evolution of Natural Language Interface for Databases (NLIDBs), the principles of language models, and the RAG paradigm, before surveying related works to identify the central research gap. Chapter 3 provides a comprehensive description of the system’s design and implementation, detailing its architecture, component specifications, and their concrete implementation. Chapter 4 is dedicated to the empirical study of the system: it begins by defining the evaluation methodology, then presents the experimental results for both SLM performance and overall system output quality, and concludes with a discussion that synthesizes the findings. Finally, Chapter 5 concludes the dissertation by summarizing the key contributions, acknowledging the study’s limitations, and outlining promising directions for future work.

Chapter 2

Theoretical Foundation and Literature Review

This chapter establishes the theoretical and empirical groundwork for the PIF intelligent agent by synthesizing foundational concepts and contextualizing the research within the current state of the art. The discussion begins with a review of NLIDBs, tracing their evolution from early rule-based systems to modern data-driven approaches. It then delves into the core technologies that power the intelligent agent: the Transformer architecture, the strategic advantages of SLMs, and the methods used to adapt them via prompt engineering. Subsequently, the chapter explains the RAG paradigm, detailing its core concepts and the role of vector databases in its implementation. Finally, this theoretical foundation is used to frame a structured review of related works, analyzing current research in RAG for database querying and V-NLIs. The chapter culminates in a discussion that identifies the specific research gap this thesis aims to address, thereby motivating the novel contributions of the proposed system.

2.1 Natural Language Interfaces for Databases

A NLIDB is a system that allows users to retrieve information from a structured database using their natural language (e.g., English, Portuguese) instead of a formal query language like Structured Query Language (SQL). The fundamental challenge in designing an NLIDB lies in bridging the significant "semantic gap" between the inherent ambiguity and flexibility of human language and the rigid, formal syntax required by database management systems. An effective NLIDB must correctly interpret a user's intent, accurately map it to the database's specific schema (its tables, columns, and relationships), and translate it into a perfectly formed, executable query.

The ultimate promise of this technology is the democratization of data. By eliminating the need for specialized training in query languages, NLIDBs empower domain experts, business analysts, and the general public to explore and analyze information directly, fostering data-driven decision-making and discovery. This section traces the evolution of NLIDBs, from the early, rule-based systems of the 1970s to the modern, machine learning-driven approaches that define the current state of the art.

2.1.1 Historical Overview

The quest to interact with databases through natural language has a rich history spanning over five decades. Early systems emerged in the 1970s, notably LUNAR, which allowed geologists to query a database of lunar rock samples collected during the Apollo missions using natural language. LUNAR employed an Augmented Transition Network (ATN) parser combined with procedural semantics to interpret queries, and could successfully answer 78% of domain questions [10].

This was followed by CHAT-80, which translated English queries into Prolog expressions for a geographical database [11]. The system's architecture—consisting of a parser, semantic interpreter, and query generator—established a template that influenced subsequent NLIDBs designs. As described in [12], these early systems relied heavily on

hand-crafted rules and domain-specific knowledge, limiting their portability across different databases and applications.

Throughout the 1980s and 1990s, systems like TEAM introduced important innovations, particularly in its approach to portability across different databases. TEAM incorporated domain-independent linguistic knowledge separate from domain-specific database information, using an intermediary knowledge representation layer [13]. This architectural approach addressed a key limitation of earlier systems, which typically required extensive reconfiguration when applied to new databases.

Other notable early systems included BASEBALL, which answered questions about baseball statistics [14], and LADDER, which provided natural language access to distributed databases containing naval information [15]. These early systems were typically domain-specific and relied heavily on hand-crafted rules and syntactic parsing [16].

2.1.2 Modern Approaches

The field of NLIDBs has evolved dramatically with advances in computational linguistics and machine learning. Modern approaches can be broadly categorized into semantic parsing methods and neural network-based techniques.

Semantic Parsing Approaches

Semantic parsing approaches represent one significant direction in modern NLIDBs, where natural language queries are translated into formal representations like SQL or logical forms [17]. These approaches typically frame the problem as a structured prediction task, mapping input utterances to executable queries.

The shift towards learning-based systems was exemplified by CHILL, a system introduced by [18] that learned to parse natural language into database queries through inductive logic programming. This work demonstrated that machine learning could reduce the manual effort required to develop an NLIDB. Furthering this trend, [19] developed a

statistical approach to semantic parsing that learns a probabilistic Combinatory Categorical Grammar (CCG). from sentences paired with their logical forms. Their system could learn to map questions to lambda-calculus expressions, showing how statistical methods could reduce the need for hand-engineered components.

To address the challenge of ambiguity, subsequent research demonstrated how interactive semantic parsing could improve accuracy. The NaLIR system, for example, incorporated user feedback to resolve interpretation ambiguities, combining linguistic parsing with schema matching to generate SQL queries that users could verify and refine through an interactive interface [20].

The introduction of the WikiSQL dataset by [21] provided a large-scale corpus of natural language questions and corresponding SQL queries, enabling broader experimentation with data-driven approaches. This dataset, containing 80,654 question-query pairs across 24,241 tables, became a benchmark for evaluating text-to-SQL models and accelerated progress in the field.

Neural Network-Based Methods

The landscape of NLIDBs has transformed dramatically in the past decade, primarily due to advances in machine learning and NLP. They began with Sequence-to-Sequence (Seq2Seq) models, which were inspired by advances in machine translation and initially proposed by [22], and were adapted for translating natural language to SQL queries.

A key development in this area was the application of an attention-based Seq2Seq architecture, which [23] demonstrated could effectively map natural language questions to logical forms, achieving state-of-the-art results on multiple semantic parsing benchmarks. Their approach encoded the input question as a sequence and decoded it into a logical form, using attention mechanisms to align parts of the output with relevant parts of the input.

The introduction of Transformer architectures [24] marked another significant advancement. Unlike previous Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Transformers use self-attention mechanisms to process input sequences in parallel, capturing long-range dependencies more effectively. [25] developed a transformer-based model for text-to-SQL generation that incorporated database schema information, showing significant improvements over previous approaches. Their model encoded both the natural language question and database schema, enabling more accurate query generation by considering the specific structure of the target database.

Further refinements have focused on improving the syntactic correctness and schema awareness of the generated SQL. For instance, PICARD, an incremental parsing method proposed by [26], constrains the decoding of Large Language Models (LLMs) to ensure syntactically valid SQL, achieving state-of-the-art results on benchmarks such as Spider [27]. In a similar vein, the RAT-SQL model from [28] incorporated relation-aware self-attention mechanisms to better capture the structure of database schemas during the query generation process, also achieving top performance on the Spider benchmark.

2.2 Large and Small Language Models

At the heart of modern NLP, and central to the capabilities of the intelligent agent in this thesis, lies the concept of the language model: a sophisticated statistical model trained on vast amounts of text data to understand and generate human language. These models serve as the cognitive engine for advanced AI systems, enabling them to interpret user intent, answer questions, and generate coherent, context-aware text.

This section explores the key developments that have defined the current generation of language models. It begins with the revolutionary Transformer architecture and its attention mechanism, the foundational technology that enabled unprecedented scalability and performance. It then examines the recent and strategic shift toward SLMs, which offer a balance of power and efficiency crucial for practical, real-world deployments. Finally, it details the primary methods for model adaptation, contrasting traditional fine-tuning with

the more dynamic and flexible paradigm of prompt engineering and in-context learning, which are fundamental to the design of the PIF agent.

2.2.1 Transformer Architecture and Attention Mechanism

The transformer architecture, introduced by [24] in their seminal paper "Attention Is All You Need," revolutionized NLP by replacing RNNs with attention mechanisms.

Figure 2.1 depicts the Transformer architecture. It consists of an encoder and decoder, each composed of stacked self-attention and feed-forward neural network layers. At the core of the Transformer is the multi-head attention mechanism, consisting of several attention layers running in parallel, which allows the model to attend to information from different representation subspaces simultaneously. For each attention head, the input is transformed into three components: queries (Q), keys (K), and values (V). The output is computed as a weighted sum of values, where the weight assigned to each value is determined by the compatibility of the corresponding query and key:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (2.1)$$

Where d_k is the dimension of the key vectors, serving as a scaling factor to prevent extremely small gradients during backpropagation [24].

This mechanism enables the model to capture complex relationships between tokens in a sequence, regardless of their distance from each other—addressing the long-range dependency problem that plagued RNNs and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [29]. The parallel computation of attention also enables more efficient training compared to sequential models.

The transformer’s encoder-decoder structure has proven remarkably versatile and scalable. The encoder processes the input sequence, while the decoder generates the output sequence, with attention mechanisms operating both within each component and between them. This architecture has formed the foundation for virtually all modern language models, from BERT [30] to GPT [31] and their successors.

Figure 2.1: Transformer architecture. Taken from [24]

2.2.2 The Rise of Small Language Models

Despite their capabilities, LLMs present trade-offs that are increasingly relevant for practical deployment in real-world systems. Large, general-purpose models such as GPT-4 and Claude excel at handling a wide variety of tasks and demonstrate impressive generalization, but their size comes at the cost of high computational requirements, significant energy consumption, and potential privacy concerns when queries are sent to external Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) [32]. These constraints have spurred the development of SLMs, such as Microsoft’s Phi-4 [33], Mistral 7B [34], and Meta’s Llama 3-8B [35]. SLMs, with parameter counts typically in the 1-10 billion range, are designed to run efficiently on consumer hardware while preserving much of the reasoning ability and language understanding of their larger counterparts.

Several factors have contributed to the viability of SLMs. First, knowledge distillation techniques allow smaller models to learn from larger ones [36]. Models like DistilBERT [37] achieved 97% of BERT’s performance with 40% fewer parameters and being 60% faster. Second, architectural improvements have enhanced efficiency; for example, MobileBERT [38] used bottleneck structures and inverted bottlenecks inspired by computer vision models.

Third, improved pre-training techniques have led to better parameter utilization. Models like ELECTRA [39] replaced the masked language modeling objective with a discriminative task, achieving better performance with fewer parameters. Finally, quantization methods reduce precision requirements without significant performance degradation; techniques like GPTQ [40] enable 4-bit quantization with minimal accuracy loss.

Recent SLMs have demonstrated impressive capabilities despite their compact size. Phi-4 (14B parameters), released by Microsoft in 2024, approaches the performance of much larger models on benchmarks like MMLU and GPQA [33]. Similarly, Llama 3 8B [35] demonstrates strong reasoning and instruction-following capabilities in a compact form factor. Mistral 7B [34] introduced grouped-query attention for efficiency while maintaining competitive performance, and Qwen2.5 7B [41] demonstrated strong multilingual capabilities.

These models offer several advantages for deployment scenarios. They can run on consumer hardware, including laptops and edge devices, reducing dependence on cloud services. This enables offline operation, addressing privacy concerns associated with sending data to external servers. Their reduced computational requirements translate to lower inference latency and operational costs. For specialized applications, SLMs can be more easily fine-tuned or adapted, making them attractive for domain-specific deployments like the PIF database interface in this thesis.

2.2.3 Model Adaptation: From Fine-tuning to Prompting

The utility of pre-trained models lies in their adaptability. Rather than training a model from scratch for every new task, researchers have developed powerful methods to steer pre-trained models toward specific objectives.

Fine-Tuning: Adapting Parametric Memory for Specific Domains

The knowledge contained within a language model’s parameters is referred to as parametric memory. Rather than storing explicit facts, these models internalize patterns and information during training, encoded in billions of parameters [31]. For instance, the Mistral 7B model [34] utilizes seven billion parameters, with the scale of parameters directly affecting both representational capacity and computational cost. Language models are often benchmarked and compared based on this parameter count, which not only influences memory and processing requirements but also reflects the breadth of information the model can potentially reproduce [42].

Parametric memory is inherently limited by the training data and the cutoff date of the corpus. This means models cannot access new or evolving information unless retrained or fine-tuned. Fine-tuning involves updating a model’s parameters (weights) using additional, domain-specific data. This process is less resource-intensive than training a foundation model from scratch and enables organizations to adapt general models to their particular needs. Fine-tuning is especially valuable where the required domain expertise cannot be found in generic corpora [43]. For instance, BioBERT [44] was obtained by fine-tuning the general-purpose BERT model on large biomedical corpora such as PubMed abstracts and PMC full-text articles. This domain adaptation significantly improved performance on tasks like biomedical named entity recognition and question answering, demonstrating how fine-tuning can specialize a model toward expert knowledge domains.

Recent advances in Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT), such as Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) [45], further decrease the computational burden by only updating a small

subset of parameters. This democratizes model adaptation, making it feasible for smaller organizations and research groups.

In-Context Learning and Prompt Engineering

A prompt is an input to a generative AI model that guides its output. Prompts may consist of text, images, audio, or other media, and they serve as the primary mechanism for interacting with LLMs [46].

The power of prompting became truly apparent with the advent of very large models, which demonstrated a remarkable new paradigm: In-Context learning (ICL). First demonstrated at scale by GPT-3, ICL is the ability of a model to learn a new task at inference time—without any parameter updates—simply by being shown a few examples within its input prompt [31]. This is often referred to as "few-shot prompting."

For instance, to perform sentiment analysis, one might include a few demonstrations in the prompt:

Tweet: "I love this new phone!" Sentiment: Positive

Tweet: "The battery life is terrible." Sentiment: Negative

Tweet: "Just got my ticket for the concert." Sentiment:

The model, having processed these examples, is expected to correctly complete the final entry (e.g., "Neutral" or "Positive"). This capability is attributed to the model's pre-training on diverse datasets, which enables it to encode a wide range of latent knowledge [31].

This paradigm places prompting—and, more specifically, prompt engineering—at the center of modern NLP development. A well-constructed prompt acts as a high-level program, steering the model's behavior. The process of iteratively refining these inputs is known as prompt engineering, where the "source code" is natural language and the goal is to constrain the model's vast generative space toward useful and accurate outputs.

Several distinct prompting strategies have been developed:

- **Zero-Shot Prompting:** The model is given a natural language instruction describing

the task but is not provided with any examples. For instance: *Classify the sentiment of the following tweet: "The movie was okay, not great but not bad either."* The model's ability to perform this task relies entirely on its pre-existing knowledge of the concept of "sentiment classification" [31].

- **Few-Shot Prompting:** This is the practical application of in-context learning, where a handful of demonstrations are included in the prompt to guide the model's response.
- **Chain-of-Thought (CoT) Prompting:** This advanced technique encourages the model to break down complex problems into intermediate reasoning steps before providing a final answer. By including few-shot exemplars that demonstrate a step-by-step thought process, the model is prompted to "think aloud." [47] showed that CoT prompting significantly improves performance on tasks requiring arithmetic, commonsense, and symbolic reasoning. For example, a CoT prompt might include a reasoning path like: *The user wants to know the total cost. First, I need to calculate the price of the items. Second, I need to add the tax. Finally, I will sum them to get the total.* This explicit reasoning process often leads to more accurate and reliable outcomes.

The design of a prompt extends beyond instructions and examples. Phrasing, tone, and even the "role" assigned to the model (e.g., *"You are an expert database administrator..."*) can measurably affect the quality and style of the output [46].

Figure 2.2 presents a conceptual flow diagram illustrating the interaction between prompt engineering and LLM. It depicts how user input, structured through instructions and contextual information, is processed by the LLM to generate an output response. For the PIF system, which relies on an SLM without task-specific fine-tuning, prompt engineering is not merely an auxiliary step but the core development process. Its ability to classify user intent, extract entities, and summarize results depends directly on the clarity and structure of the prompts. By combining ICL with advanced prompting strategies—such as structured output formats and explicit instructions—the system can elicit

Figure 2.2: Visual breakdown of prompt engineering components. Adapted from [48]

complex behavior from a model that has not been explicitly trained for the PIF database schema.

2.3 Retrieval-Augmented Generation

While language models store vast amounts of knowledge within their parameters, this "parametric memory" is inherently static and limited to the data it was trained on. This leads to two critical weaknesses: the inability to access information created after the model's training cutoff date and the risk of generating plausible but factually incorrect statements, a phenomenon known as "hallucination."

RAG is a powerful paradigm designed to address these limitations directly. Instead of relying solely on its internal knowledge, a RAG-enabled system dynamically retrieves relevant, up-to-date information from an external source—such as a database or a collection of documents—and uses this information as context to generate a more accurate and verifiable response. This hybrid approach combines the reasoning capabilities of a language model with the factual grounding of an external knowledge base.

This section explains the core principles of RAG, detailing its architecture and the critical role of vector databases and similarity search in enabling efficient information retrieval. It establishes the conceptual foundation for the RAG-based components used to provide the PIF intelligent agent with access to the PIF database and its schema.

2.3.1 Core Concept: Enhancing LLM Outputs with External Knowledge

Oposite to parametric memory, which refers to the knowledge contained within a language model’s parameters, non-parametric memory refers to external sources of information that the model can access on demand, such as databases, the Internet, or organizational repositories. This separation empowers models to answer queries using facts and documents not present during initial training, thereby circumventing the limitations of static parametric memory [6]. For example, integrating Wikipedia or proprietary organizational data enables systems to provide precise, context-aware answers in domains where knowledge changes rapidly or is highly specialized [8].

Initially presented by [6], RAG proposed a general framework that leverages the strength of pretrained parametric memory (i.e., the LLM) with non-parametric memory (i.e., a separate database) as a new way to improve the performance for knowledge-intensive tasks. RAG architectures dynamically incorporate external, non-parametric knowledge at inference time—without modifying model parameters—by retrieving semantically similar documents from a vector index (with documents and queries represented as dense embeddings; see Subsection 2.3.2) and conditioning the generator on this retrieved context. This hybrid design has been shown to improve factual grounding and enable up-to-date retrieval in knowledge-intensive applications such as biomedical Q&A and legal or scientific search, where grounding responses in verifiable external sources is critical [6], [7], [49].

Figure 2.3 illustrates the distinctions between a foundation model, fine-tuned LLMs, and RAG. In the case of a foundation model, all training data is incorporated into the language model, forming its parametric memory. With LLM fine-tuning, the model’s parameters are further refined using supplementary domain-specific datasets—such as proprietary documents—allowing the model to adapt its capabilities to specific tasks and requirements. In contrast, the RAG approach involves creating a separate database comprised of vector embeddings generated using an embedding model and contextual data,

Figure 2.3: Comparison of LLM model adaptation approaches. Adapted from [8]

which serves as the model’s non-parametric memory. Compared to fine-tuning, constructing and maintaining a vector database is considerably less resource-intensive [50], making this approach feasible for a wide range of organizations with sufficient technological capabilities.

Several recent works show that RAG architectures help overcome traditional language model weaknesses such as staleness, lack of transparency, and hallucination. Surveys by [51] and [7] note that RAG enables access to up-to-date external knowledge; [52] show that RAG enhances source attribution, improving model output verifiability; and empirical studies summarized in the hallucination surveys and frameworks (e.g., RAG-KG-IL) confirm that grounding generation on retrieved facts substantially reduces fabricated or inaccurate claims [53], [54].

The RAG architecture shown in Figure 2.4 operates as a pipeline that transforms a user query into a final response. This pipeline is typically organized into three sequential stages: retrieval, augmentation, and generation.

- Embedding model – Before retrieval can occur, both the documents stored in a vector database and the incoming query must be represented as embeddings. The same embedding model is used in both cases to ensure that semantic similarity between query and documents is meaningful.
- Retriever – The retriever compares the query embedding with those in the vector

Figure 2.4: RAG architecture based on [6].

database to identify the most relevant items, often returning the top-k results based on similarity scores. This step establishes the context for the next stage.

- **Augmentation** – The retrieved context is combined with the user query to form an augmented input. Typically, augmentation involves inserting the retrieved content into a template prompt (e.g., “Use the following context: [context]. Given this, answer the query: [query]”).
- **Generator** – The generator (usually a LLM or SLM) then produces the final output, drawing on both the original query and the augmented context. In some cases, the output may also include references or links to the original retrieved documents.

This modular design allows RAG systems to integrate external knowledge into the generation process, thereby improving factual accuracy and grounding responses in relevant evidence [8].

2.3.2 Vector Databases and Similarity Search

Central to RAG systems is the use of vector databases to store data items as high-dimensional vectors, so that at inference time a user query is also embedded and used to retrieve semantically similar documents, rather than relying purely on keyword matching. For example, [6] build a vector index over passage embeddings and retrieve based on

similarity; surveys such as [55] and the RAG architecture description in [8] similarly describe embedding-based retrieval as the core non-parametric memory component of RAG.

Several similarity metrics are commonly used to compare embeddings in vector space. Cosine similarity, which measures the cosine of the angle between two vectors, is perhaps the most widely used metric due to its effectiveness in high-dimensional spaces and invariance to vector magnitude [56]. Euclidean distance provides an alternative metric that considers the absolute distance between vectors, while other metrics like dot product and Jaccard similarity offer different trade-offs in terms of computational efficiency and semantic matching properties [57].

Vector databases like Chroma [58] and Facebook AI Similarity Search (FAISS) [59] provide efficient implementations for storing and querying high-dimensional vectors at scale. These systems employ specialized data structures and algorithms like Approximate Nearest Neighbor (ANN) search to enable efficient retrieval even with billions of vectors. These databases often incorporate additional features like metadata filtering and hybrid search capabilities, enhancing their utility for RAG applications.

2.4 Related Works

2.4.1 Literature Search Methodology

The literature review was conducted to identify recent advances in retrieval-augmented and visualization-oriented natural language interfaces relevant to the development of the intelligent agent for the PIF database. The search focused on works published between 2020 and 2025, a period marked by the emergence of RAG architectures and the proliferation of neural NLDBs.

Databases consulted included Google Scholar, IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, SpringerLink, and arXiv. Search queries combined keywords such as “retrieval-augmented

generation,” “RAG database querying,” “schema linking retrieval,” “Text-to-SQL,” “visualization natural language interface,” “domain-specific RAG system,” and “biomedical knowledge retrieval.”

The inclusion criteria targeted works that directly addressed (i) RAG or retrieval-enhanced approaches for database querying, (ii) schema retrieval and alignment for Text-to-SQL systems, and (iii) V-NLIs that enable interactive data exploration. Exclusion criteria filtered out works prior to 2020, applications unrelated to NLIDBs, and purely theoretical discussions of RAG without database context.

This search yielded three clusters of relevant contributions:

- Schema retrieval and alignment in Text-to-SQL systems, including dense embedding approaches for schema linking and retrieval-based grounding [28], [60], [61].
- Retrieval-augmented systems in domain-specific contexts, particularly biomedical and epidemiological applications such as BiomedRAG [62], BioRAGent [63], and medical question answering pipelines [64], [65], [66].
- V-NLIs, including systems such as DataTone [67], Eviza [68], and NL4DV [69], which focus on bridging language, analytics, and visualization.

These works collectively informed the conceptual and architectural foundations of the PIF intelligent agent.

2.4.2 RAG for Database Querying and Schema Retrieval

One of the applications of RAG in NLIDBs is semantic schema retrieval. Instead of directly generating a full SQL query, the system first embeds schema elements—such as table names, column labels, or metadata—into a high-dimensional vector space using an embedding model. When a user issues a natural language query, the system embeds this query using the same model and performs a similarity search against the vectorized schema. This process identifies semantically relevant database components, even when the wording differs between the user’s language and the schema terms (e.g., mapping

“*Listeria*” to “*Listeria monocytogenes*”). Empirical studies confirm that embedding-based schema retrieval improves the robustness and generalization of Text-to-SQL systems by grounding query interpretation in semantically relevant schema elements [28], [60], [61].

In this thesis, the PIF intelligent agent adopts this approach. By maintaining a vector database of the embedded schema, the system constrains the SLM’s role. Instead of generating full MongoDB queries, the SLM’s task is simplified to classifying user intent and extracting entities, which are semantically validated against the retrieved schema context. This design choice significantly reduces the risk of hallucination and ensures that all generated queries are reliable and grounded in the actual database structure.

2.4.3 V-NLIs and Their Evolution

While the primary focus of NLIDB research has been on text-to-SQL translation, recent developments have shifted toward V-NLIs, which extend querying to include visual analytics. These systems interpret natural language commands and produce data visualizations such as charts, maps, or summary plots as their outputs [70].

The core challenge for a V-NLI is resolving the inherent ambiguity and underspecification of natural language. A query like *show me Salmonella prevalence by country* does not explicitly define the visualization type (e.g., map, bar chart) or its encoding channels (e.g., axes, color). Early systems, such as Articulate, attempted to solve this with rule-based mappings from linguistic cues to predefined visualization templates, but this approach proved brittle and difficult to scale [71].

Modern approaches address this challenge by framing visualization generation as a semantic parsing problem: translating a user’s utterance into a declarative visualization specification such as Vega-Lite [72]. Some systems, like Data2Vis, employ Seq2Seq models to perform this translation directly [73]. Others, like Eviza, adopt a mixed-initiative, conversational approach, asking clarifying questions to disambiguate the user’s intent before generating a visualization [68].

The PIF system aligns with these modern V-NLI principles but addresses the ambiguity

challenge through its unique dual-mode architecture. In its Guided Meta-Analysis mode, the system entirely bypasses ambiguity by constraining the user’s choices within a structured workflow. The analytical task is so well-defined at each step that the appropriate visualization (e.g., a forest plot for a meta-analysis) can be programmatically determined without requiring the system to infer intent. In its Open Chat mode, the system infers the visualization from the classified user intent; for example, a query classified with the ‘trend_analysis‘ intent will automatically trigger the generation of a corresponding chart. This robust, hybrid approach directly addresses RQ3 by enabling non-technical users to generate complex analytical visualizations reliably and intuitively. This design situates the system at the intersection of RAG-based data access, meta-analytic computation, and interactive visualization, advancing the field toward domain-specific, explainable, and user-friendly analytical interfaces.

2.4.4 Discussion and Research Gap

The reviewed literature highlights substantial progress in integrating retrieval mechanisms and visualization capabilities into NLI. However, existing systems predominantly address general-purpose querying (e.g., Spider benchmark datasets) or biomedical question answering, with limited focus on structured, multi-source epidemiological data like that in the PIF database.

Furthermore, few systems have combined schema retrieval via RAG with domain-specific visualization pipelines for evidence synthesis and meta-analysis. The intelligent agent developed in this thesis therefore contributes novel value by:

- Applying RAG-based schema retrieval for semantically grounded query interpretation in the context of foodborne pathogen data.
- Integrating SLM-driven NLU with automated visualization and meta-analytic reporting.

- Demonstrating how domain experts in food safety can conduct exploratory analysis, trend visualization, and evidence synthesis through an intuitive conversational interface.

This integration of retrieval, reasoning, and visualization within a single intelligent agent extends the state of the art in both NLIDB and V-NLI research, while addressing a critical gap in computational epidemiology and food safety informatics.

Chapter 3

System Design

The system developed in this work aims to provide an advanced, interactive interface for data exploration, analysis, and reporting over the PIF database. This platform was designed to support food safety researchers, risk assessors, and public health agencies by automating complex data retrieval and meta-analytical tasks that traditionally require domain expertise and manual processing.

At its core, the system integrates a conversational interface with data processing and machine learning components to deliver two complementary modes of interaction:

- **Guided Meta-Analysis:** This mode provides a structured, menu-driven workflow designed to guide users through a reproducible meta-analysis. In this mode, user interaction is primarily based on selections rather than free-text input, ensuring analytical rigor and repeatability. The process begins with the user defining a specific data subset by navigating a hierarchical tree of options, including pathogen type, agent, food category, and subcategory. Once the dataset is defined, the system executes a series of predefined data preparation and analysis scripts. It presents initial descriptive summaries—interpreted by a SLM—and then proceeds with pooled prevalence analyses and other relevant meta-analyses. The workflow culminates in an option for the user to generate a comprehensive PDF report of the findings.
- **Open Chat:** The second mode offers a flexible, conversational interface where users

can interact with the PIF database using plain English. This open chat functionality is designed for free-form, exploratory data analysis. Users can ask questions (e.g., “What is the prevalence of *Listeria monocytogenes* in chicken meat in Portugal?”), request for data summaries, unique value listings, trend analysis, among others. In this mode, the intelligent agent interprets the user’s natural language query using an SLM with function calling capabilities. It translates the user’s intent into the appropriate database operations, executes the query, and presents the results in a textual or graphical format. This mode leverages RAG to understand user intent, link it to the database schema, and formulate accurate responses.

These two modes operate over the same backend infrastructure but differ in how user intent is captured and translated into analytical workflows. The Guided Mode prioritizes reproducibility and standardized analysis, whereas the open mode emphasizes exploratory research and flexible question-answering capabilities.

3.1 System Architecture

The system is designed with a distributed, service-oriented architecture that separates concerns into three distinct layers: a Frontend Layer for user interaction, a Backend Layer for logic and computation, and a Data Layer for storage and retrieval. This modular design enhances scalability, maintainability, and the integration of specialized components. A high-level representation of the architecture, illustrating these layers and their constituent components, is shown in Figure 3.1.

The architecture comprises the following key components:

- **Frontend Component:** This layer serves as the single point of user interaction, implementing the chatbot interface. It is internally divided into two primary sub-components that manage the user experience for each operational mode: the Guided Mode Component, which presents a structured, menu-driven workflow, and the Open Chat Mode Component, which provides a flexible, free-text conversational

Figure 3.1: High-level system architecture illustrating the layered interaction between the Frontend, Backend (Intelligent Agent Core and Meta-Analysis & Reporting), and Data components.

interface.

- **Intelligent Agent Core:** This is the central orchestrator of the system. It houses the primary AI logic and coordinates tasks between other components. It consists of two main modules:
 - **Machine Learning Module:** Responsible for all SLM-driven tasks, including natural language understanding (NLU), function calling (tool use), and the summarization of statistical results.
 - **Knowledge Extraction Module:** Manages all interactions with the Data Layer. It constructs and executes database queries, performs semantic entity matching using RAG principles, and enriches data retrieved from the databases.
- **Meta-Analysis and Reporting Component:** This component acts as a dedicated statistical engine, executing complex analytical workflows. Its functionality is broken down into three modules:

- **Data Preprocessing:** Cleans, transforms, and prepares the raw data for statistical analysis, handling inconsistencies and calculating necessary metrics like effect sizes.
 - **Statistical Analysis Engine:** Performs all meta-analytical computations, including descriptive statistics, pooled prevalence estimation, and multilevel meta-regression models.
 - **Dynamic Report Generator:** Compiles the final, publication-quality PDF reports by programmatically rendering R Markdown (`.Rmd`) templates that integrate text, tables, and plots generated during an analysis session.
- **Data Layer:** This layer serves as the system’s memory. It includes two specialized databases:
 - **MongoDB:** The primary data store for all PIF records, forming the non-parametric memory for the RAG pipeline. Its flexible, document-based structure is well-suited for the heterogeneous nature of the epidemiological data.
 - **ChromaDB:** A vector database that also contributes to this non-parametric memory by storing embeddings of the database schema. It is used exclusively in the Open Chat Mode to enable semantic matching between user queries and database fields.

The operational flow differs significantly between the two interaction modes. Figure 3.2 illustrates the workflow for the guided meta-analysis mode, while Figure 3.3 presents the interaction flow of the Open Chat Mode.

3.1.1 Guided Meta-Analysis Workflow

The guided workflow follows a deterministic sequence of states:

1. The user selects a dataset by navigating a decision tree of pathogen, agent, food category, and subcategory (See Figures 3.8–3.11).

2. The system queries MongoDB for the corresponding subset and sends it to the meta-analysis component for data preparation and descriptive analysis.
3. Results are summarized by the SLM and returned to the frontend.
4. The user chooses whether to continue with pooled prevalence analysis or terminate the workflow.
5. If continued, the system runs pooled prevalence models and presents the results.
6. The user may select additional variables for meta-analysis and generate a final report.

3.1.2 Open Chat Workflow

In contrast, the open chat workflow is dynamic and driven by user intent and by the SLM's function calling capability.

1. The user submits a natural language query.
2. The SLM determines the appropriate tool or function to invoke.
3. If necessary, entities are extracted from the query (e.g., agent, food type, country) and semantically matched against PIF schema stored in ChromaDB.
4. A MongoDB query is constructed and executed based on the extracted entities.
5. The retrieved data is processed, interpreted, summarized, and presented in the chat interface as text, plots, or tables.

3.2 System Specifications

The project is implemented following a microservices architecture, a design pattern where a single application is developed as a suite of small, independently deployable services.

Figure 3.2: Workflow for the guided meta-analysis mode.

Figure 3.3: Workflow for the Open Chat Mode.

This architectural choice was made to effectively separate concerns, allowing for the use of the best technology for each specific task—Python for artificial intelligence and orchestration, R for advanced statistical computation, and JavaScript for the user interface. This approach enhances modularity, scalability, and maintainability.

The following subsections provide detailed specifications for each primary service component and the data layer they rely upon. The complete source code for this project is publicly available for review¹, and subsequent discussions will refer to specific files and scripts within this repository.

3.2.1 Frontend Component

The frontend is the sole user-facing component of the PIF system, providing the chatbot interface through which all interactions occur. It is designed to be intuitive and responsive, guiding the user through analytical workflows while clearly presenting complex information. The frontend’s file structure is depicted in Figure 3.4.

The frontend is implemented using a lightweight Flask web server, which serves a single-page application built with standard HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. This technology stack was chosen to provide a fast and maintainable user interface without the overhead of larger JavaScript frameworks. Communication between the client-side JavaScript and the backend services (the Python and R servers) is handled through standard REST APIs.

¹The project repository can be accessed at [74].

Figure 3.4: Frontend structure.

3.2.2 Intelligent Agent Core Component

The Intelligent Agent Core, implemented as the Python backend server, constitutes the primary artificial intelligence and data logic engine of the system. Its principal role is to manage the SLM, performing tasks such as NLU, summarization, and function calling. It also serves as the direct interface to the data layer, handling all communication with both the MongoDB and ChromaDB databases. The server's modular structure, depicted in Figure 3.5, separates these concerns into distinct components for routing, database interaction, and model logic.

```
├─ app.py
├─ run.py
├─ databases
│  └─ chroma_db/
├─ interfaces
│  ├─ chroma_interface.py
│  ├─ embedding.py
│  └─ mongodb_interface.py
├─ model
│  ├─ prompt_functions.py
│  ├─ pif_agent.py
│  └─ pif_agent_tools.py
├─ routes
└─ api.py
```

Figure 3.5: Directory structure of the Python backend server, illustrating the separation of concerns into routes, interfaces, and model logic.

3.2.3 Meta-Analysis and Reporting Component

A core capability of the PIF intelligent agent is its ability to perform complex statistical analyses and generate comprehensive reports. This functionality is realized through the R backend server, which acts as a dedicated statistical computation engine. The R server is a specialized microservice built using the *Plumber* package, which allows R functions to be exposed as REST API endpoints. The server’s modular structure, shown in Figure 3.6, separates statistical logic into distinct scripts for data preparation, descriptive analysis, meta-analysis, and report generation.

```

├─ run_api.R
├─ plumber.R
├─ images/
├─ R
│  ├─ bacteria_data_prep.R
│  ├─ bacteria_descriptive_stats.R
│  ├─ multilevel_meta_analysis.R
│  ├─ pooled_prevalence_analysis.R
│  ├─ protozoans_data_prep.R
│  ├─ protozoans_descriptive_stats.R
│  ├─ report_generation.R
│  ├─ template_helper.R
│  ├─ template.tex
│  ├─ virus_data_prep.R
│  ├─ virus_descriptive_stats.R
│  └─ wordclouds.R

```

Figure 3.6: Directory structure of the R server.

3.2.4 Data Layer

The foundation of the PIF intelligent agent is its data layer, which is managed using MongoDB and ChromaDB. The system primarily interacts with three microbiological data collections—*bacteria*, *virus*, and *protozoa*—along with a *study* collection that contains metadata common to all records. For the Open Chat Mode, the system also relies on a ChromaDB vector database to enable RAG.

While the complete PIF database schema is extensive, the intelligent agent and its meta-analysis pipelines primarily leverage a specific subset of fields. These fields, detailed below, provide the necessary information for data filtering, statistical analysis, and reporting. For a comprehensive description of the entire database schema, readers are referred to [2]. An example of a document from the *bacteria* collection is provided in Appendix A.1.

The key fields utilized by the system are as follows:

<i>StudyID</i>	Unique identifier for the source study.
<i>Year</i>	The start year of the survey, used for temporal analysis.
<i>Agent</i>	The specific pathogenic agent detected or quantified.

<i>CountrySampling</i>	The country where the food samples were collected.
<i>Category,</i> <i>SubCategory,</i> <i>FoodClass,</i> <i>FoodSubClass,</i> <i>FoodClassSpecie</i>	A hierarchical classification of the food item.
<i>Label</i>	Description of the food sample as indicated in the study.
<i>OrganSampled</i>	The specific organ sampled for analysis, relevant for certain food types like meat or fish.
<i>TempRetail,</i> <i>RTE, PackSta-</i> <i>tus</i>	Characteristics of the food sample at the point of collection, such as temperature, ready-to-eat status, and packaging.
<i>SamplingStage</i>	The stage of the food chain from which the sample was taken.
<i>TotalUnitsTested</i>	The total number of samples analyzed in a study.
<i>SampleWDet</i>	The amount of the analytical sample used for detection assays.
<i>DetecEnrichment</i>	The number of positive samples found after enrichment.
<i>EssayDet, Es-</i> <i>sayEnum</i>	The microbiological assays used for pathogen detection and enumeration, respectively.
<i>LoQ, Greater-</i> <i>LoQ, LowerLoQ</i>	Fields related to the limit of quantification of the analytical methods.
<i>MeanConc</i>	The mean concentration value, typically in log CFU per unit.
<i>BiasPotential,</i> <i>BiasType</i>	Indicators of potential bias in the study's methodology.

3.3 Implementation

3.3.1 Frontend Implementation

The core Flask application, defined in *app.py* and executed via *run.py*, is responsible for serving the main *index.html* template and static assets. Communication with backend services is handled by the logic within *api.js*, which initiates asynchronous HTTP requests (e.g., using the *fetch* API) to defined endpoints on the backend servers.

User Interface and Workflow Selection

Upon loading the application, the user is presented with a welcome message and two distinct workflow options: “Guided Meta-Analysis and Reporting” and “Explore the PIF Database” (Figure 3.7). This initial choice, managed by *initializer.js* and *dom.js*, directs the user into one of the two chatbot modes.

Figure 3.7: Initial user interface presenting the two primary workflow options.

A key feature of the Guided Mode is the use of “Smart Trees” for dataset selection (Figures 3.8–3.11). These are dynamically generated, hierarchical menus that only present pathogen, agent, and food combinations for which there are sufficient data (a minimum of three records) to perform a meaningful meta-analysis. This pre-filtering queries the MongoDB database, counts records for each combination, and writes the resulting tree structures as JSON files to the *public/data/* directory. The frontend then dynamically loads these JSON files via a dedicated Flask route to render the selection trees.

The first tree guides users through selecting the relevant pathogen by presenting all pathogen categories for which sufficient data are available.

 Which type of pathogen are you interested in?

Figure 3.8: Pathogen selection tree.

Once a pathogen is chosen, the second tree narrows the options to compatible agents, ensuring that users only see agent selections that are supported by adequate underlying data.

 Which agent are you interested in?

Figure 3.9: Agent selection tree for pathogen “Bacteria”.

After an agent is selected, the third tree presents the available high-level food categories, helping users to focus the analysis on the most relevant parts of the food system.

Which food category are you interested in?

Figure 3.10: Food category tree for agent *Listeria monocytogenes*.

The final tree refines the selection further by listing specific food subcategories within the chosen category, enabling precise definition of the dataset to be included in the meta-analysis.

Which food subcategory are you interested in?

submit

Figure 3.11: Food subcategory tree for food category “Meat and meat products”.

The open chat interface provides a text-based conversational environment where users can submit free-form questions, as shown in Figure 3.12.

All right! Let's explore the PIF database together.

Getting Started: Quick Guide

The open chat module supports natural, plain English questions using a **small language model with function calling** capabilities. This means you can simply type your query without needing to know any specific syntax.

Important: The system is currently **under development**, so it can only respond to a limited range of questions based on the tools available in its current toolbox.

Here are a few examples of the types of questions you can ask:

```
Show me data on Salmonella in Portugal
```

```
What is the prevalence of Listeria in dairy products in Spain?
```

```
How has the prevalence of Salmonella in poultry changed over the years?
```

Entity Extraction: The bot automatically identifies key entities in your question - such as pathogen, food item, country, sampling stage, and more - to form precise queries and fetch relevant data. This enables you to ask anything from simple to very specific questions.

For further assistance, click on the **top-right tools icon** .

Ask PIF

0/200

Figure 3.12: Open chat UI.

Workflow Management via State Machine

The conversational flow of the chatbot is managed by a client-side finite state machine. The *globals.js* file formally defines the possible states for both the guided meta-analysis (*gb_states*) and the open chat (*oc_states*). The *csm_variables* object tracks the application's current state, including which mode is active and whether the system is awaiting a response from a backend server. This state-driven design is particularly critical in the Guided Mode. The *guided_bot.js* logic transitions the user between the states defined in *gb_states*—from the initial *TREE* selection phase through the various *META-DATA_ANALYSIS* steps. Each user action or server response triggers a state transition,

which in turn determines the next set of options or information presented to the user. This ensures that the complex, multi-step analytical process is executed in a controlled and logical sequence, providing a robust and predictable user experience.

3.3.2 Intelligent Agent Implementation

The agent’s ability to extract knowledge is fundamentally dependent on its integration with the data layer. This is handled by the modules within the *interfaces* directory.

Database Interfaces

The *mongodb_interface.py* module provides all functionality for connecting to and querying the PIF MongoDB database. The core function, *execute_mongo_query*, receives a query object, connects to the appropriate collection, and executes the query. A crucial step in this process is data enrichment, handled by the *enrich_with_study_data* function. After retrieving the primary records, this function performs a secondary lookup in the *study* collection using the *StudyID* to join relevant study-level metadata, such as *Year* and *DurationSurvey*, to each record. This ensures that the data passed to the meta-analysis component and the SLM is complete for analysis and interpretation.

The *chroma_interface.py* module provides the functions for interacting with the vector database at runtime. The vector database is populated by a series of setup scripts (e.g., *agent_schema_db_setup.py*, *food_category_schema_db_setup.py*), which generate vector embeddings for schema terms using the *all-MiniLM-L6-v2* model.

Key functions are:

- *find_top_match_for_entity*: This function takes a single text entity extracted from a user’s query (e.g., “chicken meat”) and a target ChromaDB collection. It generates an embedding for the entity and queries the collection to find the best match based on vector similarity (distance).
- *find_best_food_match*: Since food items can be described at various levels of specificity (category, subcategory, class, subclass), this specialized function searches

across multiple food-related collections and returns the single best match with the lowest distance score, resolving ambiguity in food-related queries.

- *match_entities_to_schema*: This function orchestrates the entire schema-linking process. It takes a dictionary of entities extracted by the SLM and uses the functions above to find the best-matching formal schema term for each entity, effectively translating the user’s natural language into structured, queryable data points.

The PIF Agent and Tool-Using Architecture

The core of the open chat functionality is the *PIFAgent* class, implemented in *pif_agent.py*. This class embodies a modern, tool-using AI architecture, where a SLM acts as a reasoning engine to select and parameterize a set of predefined Python functions (“tools”). This design pattern allows the system to combine the NLU capabilities of the SLM with the reliability and precision of deterministic code execution.

Upon receiving a user’s question via the */api/qa* endpoint, the agent’s main *run_question* method executes a two-step process:

1. *Tool Selection*: The user’s question is sent to the machine learning module along with a system prompt and a schema of all available tools. The SLM analyzes the user’s intent and select the single most appropriate tool, returning its choice as a structured JSON object.
2. *Tool Execution*: The server parses the SLM’s response, identifies the chosen function (e.g., *dataset_summary*, *get_prevalence_by_food*), and executes it with the parameters provided by the SLM. The output of this function is then returned to the user.

The agent is equipped with a comprehensive set of tools, defined in the *_build_tools_registry* method, designed to cover a wide range of data exploration and analysis tasks. These include functions for data loading (*dataset_load*), metadata inspection (*dataset_list_columns*, *dataset_column_description*), data summarization (*dataset_summary*, *dataset*

_records_by_group), and specific analytical queries (*get_prevalence_by_food*, *trend_analysis*). The schema for each tool, defined in the *_build_tools_schema* method, provides the SLM with a detailed description of the tool’s purpose, its parameters, and which parameters are required, guiding it to make accurate selections.

This architecture is inherently extensible. To add new capabilities to the agent, a developer only needs to implement a new Python function and then register it by adding it to the tool registry and defining its corresponding schema. This modularity allows the system’s analytical capabilities to be expanded without altering the core reasoning logic of the agent.

Prompt Engineering and Specialized Functions

Beyond the core tool-using agent, the system’s intelligence is significantly refined by a suite of specialized, prompt-driven functions managed within the *prompt_functions.py* module. This module encapsulates the logic for complex, domain-specific tasks that require nuanced natural language understanding and controlled text generation, such as entity extraction, statistical interpretation, and meta-analysis synthesis.

These functions are invoked differently depending on the interaction mode. In the guided meta-analysis, they are called directly by the server in response to explicit API requests (e.g., */api/meta-analysis-summary*). In the open chat, they are dynamically selected and executed as part of the *PIFAgent*’s reasoning process, following the principles of tool-augmented language modeling.

A key design principle of the PIF intelligent agent is the explicit separation between the system prompt and the user prompt. The system prompt establishes the SLM’s identity, role, and behavioral constraints—for instance, defining it as an “expert biostatistical assistant” or a “specialized entity extraction engine.” It encodes persistent behavioral rules (e.g., “always return valid JSON,” “limit responses to two sentences”) to ensure consistency. The user prompt, conversely, provides the task-specific context—such as dataset statistics, study metadata, or a user’s natural-language query. This layered structure maintains a strict behavioral boundary between what the model is and what it must do,

leading to more predictable and reproducible outputs.

Prompting Strategies To maximize reliability and domain precision, a hybrid of prompting techniques is employed, combining structured templates with real-time data retrieved from MongoDB and processed by the statistical analysis engine. The primary strategies include:

1. **Zero-shot Instruction Prompting:** Functions such as *summarize_pooled_prevalence* or *summarize_meta_analysis* rely on this technique, where the model receives a clear, rule-based task description without any examples. For instance, the *pooled_prevalence_analysis_system_prompt* instructs the model to analyze JSON input, identify key values, and return a concise, two-sentence interpretation. This approach is ideal for deterministic summarization tasks where strict output constraints (e.g., "plain text only," "two-sentence limit") are necessary to minimize hallucination.
2. **Structured Context Prompting:** Prompts like *bacteria_subset_summary* are examples of context-rich prompting. Here, structured data (e.g., country distributions, bias statistics) is directly injected into the user prompt as formatted lists or JSON blocks. This strategy grounds the model's generation in factual data, resulting in a coherent, data-driven synthesis that accurately reflects the dataset's characteristics.
3. **Role-based Prompting:** Each specialized function assigns a distinct persona to the model through its system prompt. For example, the prompt for entity extraction positions the model as a deterministic parsing engine that must return a rule-based, JSON-only response. This role-based constraint ensures outputs are machine-readable and free of conversational artifacts, making them ideal for subsequent programmatic use.
4. **Implicit Chain-of-Thought:** Although not exposed to the user, internal workflows implement modular reasoning chains. When interpreting meta-analysis outputs, for instance, the system decomposes the process into subtasks—statistical

summarization, bias assessment, and moderator evaluation—each guided by its own prompt. This distributes the reasoning across specialized components, enhancing explainability.

5. **Hybrid Prompt Composition:** Complex tasks, such as the final interpretation of a meta-analysis, employ hybrid prompts that combine structured context, analytical instructions, and domain-specific vocabulary. By embedding definitions for statistical terms (e.g., “tau-squared,” “QEp,” “R²”), the model’s interpretative behavior is regularized, reducing domain misunderstanding and ensuring terminological consistency.

Application: Entity Extraction for Query Construction A cornerstone of the Open Chat Mode is the *extract_entities_from_input* function, which exemplifies the use of role-based, instruction-driven prompting. This function is responsible for translating a user’s unstructured query into a structured set of key-value pairs for building a formal database query. It employs a highly detailed system prompt (*extract_entities_from_input_system_prompt*) that instructs the SLM to act as a specialized entity extraction engine.

The prompt defines an order of operations to resolve ambiguity (e.g., identifying specific entities like *rte_status* before a broader *food_item*) and provides precise definitions for each entity, including synonyms. It mandates a strict JSON output format where all possible keys must be present, even if their value is *null*. This rigorous, rule-based prompting transforms the general-purpose SLM into a predictable and accurate parsing tool, forming the critical first step in the RAG pipeline for query construction.

This modular, prompt-driven approach forms the linguistic backbone of the PIF agent’s reasoning architecture, enabling consistent domain behavior while remaining flexible enough to incorporate new analytical capabilities.

Execution Environment and Inference Parameters

All SLM interactions within these specialized functions are executed locally through the *Ollama* framework using its chat API endpoint (<http://localhost:11434/api/chat>).

To ensure reliable and reproducible outputs, inference is configured with a *temperature* of 0.0 and a *top_p* of 0.1. A zero temperature makes generation deterministic, while the *top_p* parameter (nucleus sampling) restricts output to the smallest subset of tokens whose cumulative probability exceeds 0.1 [75], [76]. This setup minimizes randomness, ensuring factual, consistent results—essential for tasks such as entity extraction, scientific summarization, and statistical interpretation, where creativity would be undesirable.

3.3.3 Meta-Analysis and Reporting Implementation

The analytical pipeline is a multi-stage process that begins with data preparation and progresses through several layers of analysis.

Data Preprocessing and Analysis

Due to schema differences, a pathogen-specific data preparation script is required (e.g., *bacteria_data_prep*). This function unnests JSON structures, converts data types, calculates a unified prevalence value, computes effect sizes (y_i , v_i) using the *escalc* function from the *metafor* package, and data cleaning.

Following preprocessing, descriptive analysis is performed by functions like *bacteria_generate_descriptive_stats*, which computes summary statistics, such as the number of studies, frequency counts for key categorical variables (e.g., country, ready-to-eat status), and data quality metrics. This function returns a structured JSON object, which is then sent to the SLM for summarization into a human-readable text.

Pooled prevalence analyses are then executed (e.g., *pooled_prevalence_by_pack_status*), which perform random-effects meta-analyses using the *rma.mv* function for each category of a given moderator. The data results are used to generate a forest plot, which is returned as a binary image. Crucially, the function also returns a structured data table containing the pooled prevalence, confidence intervals, and study/record counts for each category. This table is subsequently passed to the SLM for interpretation.

Multilevel Meta-Analysis

The final analytical stage is user-driven. The *determine_applicable_variables* function first identifies which potential moderators (e.g., *FoodSubCategory*, *OrganSampled*, *Essay-Detection*) have sufficient data variability. This list of valid moderators is presented to the user in the frontend, as shown in Figure 3.13.

Upon user selection, a comprehensive meta-analysis function (e.g., *multilevel_meta_analysis_by_essay_detection*) is executed. This function generates exploratory plots, runs a multilevel model using *rma.mv* with the selected moderator as a fixed effect and *StudyID* as a random effect, extracts key statistics (τ^2 , Q_{MP} , R^2), and performs publication bias assessment using funnel plots and formal tests. It returns all generated plots as binary images and the summary statistics as structured data tables to the SLM for interpretation.

Meta-analysis can be done by:

- Food Subcategory
- Food Class
- Food Subclass
- Food Class Specie
- Organ Sampled
- Essay Detection
- Mean Concentration

Which one would you like to analyze?

Figure 3.13: User interface showing the dynamically determined list of available variables for multilevel meta-analysis for *Toxoplasma* in Meat and meat products.

Dynamic Report Generation

The reporting feature automates the creation of a complete PDF report. The process begins when the frontend sends all session assets (plots, tables, text) to the Python server's

/api/generate-report endpoint. The *generate_report* function dynamically constructs an R Markdown (`.Rmd`) document using these assets, inserting placeholders for figures and tables alongside the SLM-generated summaries.

This `.Rmd` text is then passed to the *render_report* function on the R server. This function creates a temporary directory, saves all assets, programmatically replaces the placeholders with R code chunks (*knitr::include_graphics* for images, *kableExtra* for tables), and finally calls *rmarkdown::render* to compile the document into a PDF using a custom LaTeX template. The resulting PDF is returned to the user for download.

Chapter 4

Experiments, Results and Discussion

This chapter details the empirical evaluation of the PIF Intelligent Agent, presenting the complete methodology, the resulting data, and a discussion of the findings. The chapter begins by establishing the Evaluation Methodology (Section 4.1), which includes the experimental setup, the definition of all performance metrics, and the specific procedures used to assess both the Open Chat and Guided Meta-Analysis modes.

Following the methodology, the chapter presents the Results, starting with a quantitative comparison of the SLMs in the Open Chat Mode to address their performance in NLU and text generation. It then reports on the system’s end-to-end analytical and visualization outputs, including a detailed case study of the Guided Meta-Analysis mode. The chapter concludes with a comprehensive discussion that synthesizes these findings and interprets their significance in relation to the research questions.

4.1 Evaluation Methodology

To quantitatively and qualitatively assess the performance, interpretability, and analytical reliability of the PIF Intelligent Agent, a clear distinction was made between metrics evaluating the core SLM and those assessing the broader system’s outputs. This separation forms the basis of the evaluation frameworks for both the Guided Meta-Analysis Mode and the Open Chat Mode.

4.1.1 Experimental Setup

All experiments were conducted in a controlled computing environment running Ubuntu 24.04.3 LTS. The hardware configuration was selected to support both the backend data processing and local evaluation of SLMs capable of function calling and contextual reasoning. Table 4.1 summarizes the key hardware specifications used for testing.

To ensure fair comparability and reproducibility across all tests involving language models, each model was evaluated under identical hyperparameter settings. A deterministic configuration was chosen by setting the *temperature* = 0.0 and *top-p* = 0.1. This minimizes randomness in the model’s output, making the results consistent and directly comparable.

Table 4.1: Hardware specifications of the experimental testbed.

Component	Specification
Operating System	Ubuntu 24.04.3 LTS
CPU	AMD EPYC 9554P (32 Cores)
System Memory (RAM)	125.79 GB
GPU	NVIDIA GRID A100D-16C
GPU Memory (VRAM)	16 GB
NVIDIA Driver Version	550.127.05
CUDA Version	12.4
Disk Space (SSD)	252 GB

4.1.2 Evaluation Metrics

A set of metrics was defined to assess two distinct components: the performance of the SLM itself and the quality of the system’s analytical outputs. This distinction, detailed in Table 4.2, is crucial for pinpointing the source of the agent’s successes or failures.

Table 4.2: Evaluation metrics for the PIF Intelligent Agent, categorized by the component being evaluated.

Evaluation Category	Metric	Type	Definition	Measurement Method
SLM Performance (Open Chat Mode)	Intent Classification Accuracy (ICA)	Quantitative	Accuracy of the selected tool/function call.	Correct/Total ratio (%).
	Entity Extraction F1-score (EEF1)	Quantitative	Accuracy and completeness of extracted parameters.	F1-score.
	Data Integrity (DI)	Quantitative	Correct data subset retrieval based on SLM outputs.	Binary correctness rate (%).
	Interpretation Quality and Coherence (IQC)	Qualitative	Logical and factual quality of SLM-generated text.	Expert rating (1-5 scale).
SLM Performance (Guided Mode)	Interpretation Quality and Coherence (IQC)	Qualitative	Logical and factual quality of SLM-generated text.	Expert rating (1-5 scale).
System Output Quality (Both Modes)	Analytical Consistency (AC)	Quantitative	Statistical accuracy of the R-server's analytical pipeline.	Expert verification against R outputs.
	Visual Informativeness (VI)	Qualitative	Clarity and correctness of R-server's generated figures.	Expert rating (1-5 scale).

Detailed Metric Descriptions

To clarify their purpose, the metrics are described below based on the component they evaluate.

SLM Performance Metrics. These metrics are designed to evaluate the core capabilities of the SLM in interpreting natural language, driving the agent’s workflow, and generating textual summaries.

- **Intent Classification Accuracy (ICA):** This quantitative metric measures the fundamental ability of the SLM to understand the user’s primary goal. It is calculated as the percentage of times the model correctly selects the appropriate tool (i.e., the correct Python function) from the tool registry in response to a user’s query. A high ICA is essential, as selecting the wrong tool leads to a complete failure to address the user’s request.
- **Entity Extraction F1-score (EEF1):** This metric evaluates the model’s proficiency at identifying and extracting the specific parameters (entities) from the user’s query, such as pathogen names, food items, or countries. The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision (the accuracy of extracted entities) and recall (the completeness of extracted entities). This combined score is critical because the accuracy of the final database query depends on extracting all the correct entities without inventing incorrect ones.

- **Data Integrity (DI):** This is a strict, quantitative measure of whether the system retrieved the correct data subset from the database. It is measured as a binary correctness rate (100% for a perfect match, 0% for any error). For a query to pass the DI test, the retrieved dataset must perfectly align with the user’s intent and extracted entities, with no missing or extraneous records. This metric ensures the foundational data for any analysis is correct.
- **Interpretation Quality and Coherence (IQC):** This qualitative metric evaluates the text generated by the SLM to summarize or interpret results. Experts rate the text on a 1-to-5 scale for its logical flow, factual soundness (i.e., consistency with the data), and adherence to a scientific tone. A high IQC score indicates that the model can not only process data but also communicate its meaning effectively.

System Output Quality Metrics. These metrics assess the reliability and usability of the outputs generated by the system’s non-SLM components, primarily the statistical and visualization pipelines executed on the R server.

- **Analytical Consistency (AC):** This quantitative metric verifies the statistical correctness of the system’s calculations. It is measured by having a human expert independently perform the same analysis (e.g., a meta-analysis) on the same data subset using standard R scripts. The numerical results from the system (e.g., pooled prevalence, confidence intervals, p-values) are then compared to the expert’s results. It is measured as a binary correctness rate (100% for a perfect match, 0% for any error). A high AC score demonstrates that the system’s automated analytical pipeline is as reliable as a manual analysis.
- **Visual Informativeness (VI):** This qualitative metric assesses the quality of the generated visualizations (e.g., forest plots, bar charts). On a 1-to-5 scale, experts rate the figures based on their clarity, correctness of labeling, and ease of interpretation. This metric measures the effectiveness of the system in communicating complex data visually.

4.1.3 Evaluation of the Open Chat Mode

The selection of the SLM is a critical factor influencing the agent’s performance. This evaluation focuses on the core reasoning and generation capabilities of the underlying SLM by benchmarking the default model (*MF Doom/deepseek-r1-tool-calling:14b*) against four alternatives. These candidates were chosen to represent a spectrum of modern architectures, from a state-of-the-art LLM to several prominent SLMs. For consistency and to reflect the primary focus of this thesis on more compact systems, the term SLM will be used hereafter to refer to all models under evaluation.

The first evaluated model, *Gemini 2.5 Pro*, developed by Google DeepMind, represents a state-of-the-art multimodal system with advanced reasoning and function-calling capabilities, optimized for real-world analytical workflows [77]. The second model, *Cogito 14B*, proposed by Deep Cogito, integrates neurobiologically inspired mechanisms for cognitive reasoning and adaptive memory management, which allow it to perform complex reasoning and code-generation tasks [78]. The third candidate, *Qwen 3 (8B)*, is part of Alibaba Cloud’s Qwen model family, known for strong instruction-following performance and balanced efficiency across multilingual and domain-specific tasks [79]. Lastly, *Phi-4 Mini (3.8B)* from Microsoft offers a compact, high-performance language model optimized for reasoning under computational constraints [80].

Performance was measured using the metrics directly attributable to the SLM’s performance in this mode: ICA, EEF1, DI, and IQC. While AC and VI are also recorded during these tests to ensure end-to-end system integrity, they are not used to compare the SLMs, as those metrics evaluate a separate, model-independent component of the system.

To provide a single, holistic measure of an SLM’s utility, an overall Small Language Model Performance Index (SLMPI) was computed as the weighted geometric mean of the four SLM-specific metrics. This index emphasizes both functional correctness and interpretive quality. The geometric mean was chosen as it heavily penalizes poor performance in any single metric, ensuring that only models with balanced, all-around competence achieve a high score. The weights are assigned to reflect the priorities of a real-world

analysis, prioritizing functional correctness (DI, EEF1, ICA) while still valuing the quality of the final interpretation (IQC).

Dataset Curation for Open Chat Mode

To facilitate this quantitative evaluation, a curated "gold standard" dataset of ten representative natural language queries was constructed. This dataset, detailed in Tables 4.3 and 4.4, simulates realistic user interactions and is designed to test the full range of the agent’s function-calling capabilities. Each query is mapped to a ground-truth intent (the correct tool to call) and a precise JSON object of expected entities. The queries were specifically chosen to test distinct semantic features, from simple metadata requests (e.g., "What columns are there?") to complex analytical questions requiring multiple entity extractions (e.g., "What is the prevalence of Listeria in cheese in Portugal?").

Table 4.3: Gold standard questions and their corresponding target tools (intents).

ID	Target Tool (Intent)	Natural Language Question
Q1	Load dataset on Salmonella in Portugal.	<code>dataset_load</code>
Q2	What columns are there in the dataset?	<code>dataset_list_columns</code>
Q3	What does the column RTE mean?	<code>dataset_column_description</code>
Q4	List unique values of column PackStatus.	<code>dataset_unique_values</code>
Q5	How many records for each Category?	<code>dataset_records_by_group</code>
Q6	Provide a summary of the dataset.	<code>dataset_summary</code>
Q7	What is the prevalence of Listeria in cheese in Portugal?	<code>get_prevalence_by_food</code>
Q8	What is the average concentration of Staphylococcus in composite dish in Turkey?	<code>get_concentration_stats</code>
Q9	Which foods are most associated with Norovirus?	<code>get_food_sources_for_pathogen</code>
Q10	Has Hepatovirus A prevalence in molluscs increased from 2010 to 2025?	<code>trend_analysis</code>

Table 4.4: Expected entities (JSON arguments) for the gold standard questions.

ID	Expected Entities (JSON Argument)
Q1	"agent": "Salmonella", "country_sampling": "Portugal", ...
Q2	N/A
Q3	N/A
Q4	N/A
Q5	N/A
Q6	N/A
Q7	"agent": "Listeria", "food_item": "cheese", "country_sampling": "Portugal", ...
Q8	"agent": "Staphylococcus", "food_item": "composite dish", "country_sampling": "Turkey", ...
Q9	"agent": "Norovirus", ...
Q10	"agent": "Hepatovirus A", "food_item": "molluscs", ...

4.1.4 Evaluation of the Guided Meta-Analysis Mode

The guided workflow was evaluated through a comprehensive case study. A complete analytical report on the prevalence of *Toxoplasma* in *Meat and meat products* was automatically generated by the system. This dataset, comprising 153 records from 65 studies (1988–2023) across multiple European countries, provided a realistic and complex scenario to test the end-to-end pipeline.

The generated report, which included data descriptions, exploratory analyses, pooled prevalences analyses, and multiple multilevel meta-analyses, was subsequently reviewed by a panel of microbiologists and food safety specialists. The evaluation focused on assessing the report’s scientific adequacy according to the three metrics defined in Table 4.2: AC, VI, and IQC. Each section of the report was rated independently by the domain experts. To form a final assessment, a composite RQI was computed as the weighted mean of all criteria, assigning higher weight to AC and IQC to reflect their critical importance in scientific reporting.

4.2 SLM Performance in the Open Chat Mode

This section directly addresses Specific Objective 1 and provides a quantitative answer to RQ2. The experiment compared the performance of five SLMs on the "gold standard" dataset: *Phi-4 Mini (3.8B)* (Model 1), *MFDoom/deepseek-r1-tool-calling (14B)* (Model 2), *Cogito (14B)* (Model 3), *Qwen 3 (8B)* (Model 4), and *Gemini 2.5 Pro* (Model 5). The evaluation was based on the four metrics designed to assess SLM performance: ICA, EEF1, DI, and IQC.

4.2.1 Core Functional Performance

The initial evaluation focused on the core functional reliability of the models: their ability to correctly understand user intent, extract parameters, and ensure the retrieval of the correct data. As shown in Table 4.5, all five models demonstrated flawless performance on these metrics, achieving perfect 100% scores for ICA, EEF1, and DI.

This is a significant finding, indicating that for well-defined, tool-based tasks within a specific domain, modern instruction-tuned SLMs are exceptionally robust. The perfect DI scores, in particular, confirm that every model was able to provide the correct parameters to the system’s backend, leading to the retrieval of the exact data subset intended by the user’s query. This establishes a high baseline of technical competence for all tested models.

Table 4.5: Core functional performance metrics for all evaluated SLMs in the Open Chat Mode. All models achieved perfect scores.

Metric	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Intent Classification Accuracy (ICA)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Entity Extraction F1-score (EEF1)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Data Integrity (DI)	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

4.2.2 Interpretive Performance

With functional performance established as a constant, the evaluation focused on the qualitative aspect of the models' outputs, where significant performance gaps emerged. The IQC metric, which assesses the quality of the SLM-generated text, proved to be the key differentiator. While the first five questions in the dataset did not require a textual interpretation, the remaining five analytical questions revealed considerable variance in the quality of the generated summaries.

Table 4.6 details the average expert ratings for each model on a per-question basis. This granular view shows that while some models, like Model 1 (*Phi-4 Mini*), were highly inconsistent—scoring as low as 1.33 on one question and as high as 3.33 on another—the top-tier models (3, 4, and 5) demonstrated more stable and reliable performance. The overall mean scores confirm a clear performance hierarchy.

Table 4.6: Mean IQC scores by question for each evaluated SLM (1–5 scale).

Question	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
"Provide a summary of the dataset."	2.67	3.67	4.67	4.33	4.67
"What is the prevalence of Listeria...?"	3.00	1.67	4.33	4.67	4.67
"What is the average concentration...?"	1.33	4.67	4.67	4.33	4.67
"Which foods are most associated...?"	3.33	4.00	4.67	4.33	4.67
"Has Hepatovirus A prevalence increased...?"	3.33	4.33	5.00	5.00	4.33
Overall Mean	2.73	3.67	4.67	4.53	4.60
Standard Deviation	0.83	1.18	0.24	0.30	0.15

To make these quantitative scores tangible, the following examples compare the best and worst textual outputs for specific questions, based on the expert ratings and comments.

Example 1: Hallucination vs. Factual Accuracy. For the query "What is the prevalence of Listeria in cheese in Portugal?", Model 2 (*MFDoom/deepseek...*) received the lowest score (1.67), while Models 4 and 5 were rated highest (4.67). The reason was a critical failure: Model 2 completely hallucinated its response, reporting a prevalence of 4.98% based on incorrect record and sample counts (Figure 4.2). In contrast,

the best models accurately reported the correct prevalence of 2.32% (Figure 4.1). This demonstrates the significant risk posed by an inconsistent model.

Based on an analysis of 13 records from 7 studies... the mean prevalence of... Listeria monocytogenes in... Cheese was determined to be 2.32%.

Figure 4.1: Excerpt from the accurate summary by Model 5, rated 4.67/5.

Based on 27 records and a total of 4,576 samples tested... the weighted mean prevalence percentage of Listeria was calculated as 4.98%...

Figure 4.2: Excerpt from the hallucinated summary by Model 2, rated 1.67/5.

Example 2: Uninformative vs. Informative Output. For the query "What is the average concentration of Staphylococcus...?", Model 1 (*Phi-4 Mini*) failed completely, scoring just 1.33. It was unable to retrieve the data and instead produced a generic, uninformative template response (Figure 4.3). The other four models all scored highly (4.33-4.67) by correctly accessing the data and reporting the mean concentration of 3.03 log CFU/g (Figure 4.4).

The average concentration of Staphylococcus aureus... is approximately log CFU/g... this summary encompasses data derived from 79 records where measurements were available.

Figure 4.3: The uninformative response from Model 1, rated 1.33/5.

The analysis of Staphylococcus aureus... revealed a mean concentration of 3.03 log CFU/g across the dataset, based on 15 records out of 79 total entries...

Figure 4.4: An example of a correct summary from Model 3, rated 4.67/5.

Example 3: Summarizing Visual and Statistical Data. For the query "Has Hepatovirus A prevalence in molluscs increased from 2010 to 2025?", Model 3 and Model 4 achieved perfect 5/5 scores for their textual summaries. Both models correctly interpreted the linear regression analysis, stating that the trend was a non-significant decrease ($p > 0.05$). Both successfully identified key data points, such as the mean prevalence and the

year with the highest recorded prevalence. Figure 4.5 and Figure 4.6 show these exemplary outputs, which effectively complement the visual data shown in Figure 4.7 with a concise statistical summary.

The prevalence of Hepatovirus A in molluscs showed considerable temporal variation between 2010 and 2025, with an overall mean prevalence of 4.3%... The highest recorded prevalence was 20.0% in 2018, while several years showed zero detection... A linear regression analysis of the temporal trend revealed a non-significant decrease of -0.36 percentage points per year ($p = 0.456$), indicating no statistically significant change in prevalence over time.

Figure 4.5: Excerpt from the perfect-scoring trend analysis summary by Model 3.

The temporal trend of Hepatovirus A prevalence in the food_category Molluscs was analyzed for the period between 2010 and 2023... the observed annual prevalence of the pathogen varied, with a mean of 4.3%, ranging from a minimum of 0.0% to a maximum of 20.0%. A linear regression analysis indicated a decreasing trend with a slope of -0.36 percentage points per year, although this change was not statistically significant ($p=0.46$).

Figure 4.6: Excerpt from the similarly perfect-scoring summary by Model 4.

4.3 System Output Quality Assessment

While the previous section evaluated the SLM’s direct performance, this section assesses the quality of the downstream system outputs that are generated as a result of the SLM’s function calls: the statistical calculations and visual plots. These metrics are essential for verifying the end-to-end reliability of the agent.

Analytical Consistency (AC). The AC metric verifies the mathematical correctness of the R-server’s analytical pipeline. For every query in the Open Chat evaluation that triggered a statistical calculation (e.g., calculating mean prevalence, average concentration, or a regression slope), the results were independently verified by an expert. In all cases, the system achieved a perfect 100% AC score. This is a critical finding, as it proves that once the SLM correctly identifies the intent and entities, the system’s backend performs its calculations with complete accuracy, matching the gold standard of a manual

expert analysis.

Visual Informativeness (VI). The query "Has Hepatovirus A prevalence in molluscs increased from 2010 to 2025?" was the only one in the Open Chat evaluation to produce a visual plot (Figure 4.7). This plot was highly rated by the expert panel, receiving a mean VI score of 4.83 out of 5.

Figure 4.7: Temporal trend analysis of Hepatovirus A prevalence in molluscs (2010-2025), generated by the Open Chat mode. The figure displays the observed annual prevalence rates (circles) with 95% confidence intervals and the linear regression trend line.

4.4 Case Study: The Guided Meta-Analysis Mode

This section provides a deep dive into the end-to-end performance of the Guided Mode, using the comprehensive case study of the automatically generated report on *Toxoplasma* in *Meat and meat products*. The evaluation synthesizes all relevant metrics to assess the system's ability to support non-technical users in conducting complex, reproducible research, directly addressing RQ3.

4.4.1 Qualitative Analysis of Generated Report Content

The overall quality of the generated report hinges on both its visual clarity and the coherence of its textual interpretations. This section analyzes both components.

Visual Informativeness of Figures

The VI of the ten distinct types of figures generated for the report was a key component of the evaluation. As shown in Table 4.7, the system achieved a high average score of 4.83 out of 5, indicating a strong overall performance.

Table 4.7: Mean VI ratings for figures generated in the Guided Mode case study, averaged across three expert evaluators.

Figure Type	Mean Rating (1-5)
Figure 1: Word cloud of food type	5.00
Figure 2: Word cloud of assay type	5.00
Figure 3: Pooled prevalence analysis by year	4.00
Figure 4: Pooled prevalence analysis by sampling stage	5.00
Figure 5: Pooled prevalence analysis by pack status	5.00
Figure 6: Pooled prevalence analysis by temperature of sampling	5.00
Figure 7: Pooled prevalence analysis by ready-to-eat status	5.00
Figures 8, 11, 14, 17: Number of records (Bar plots)	5.00
Figures 9, 12, 15, 18: Prevalence distribution (Ridge plots)	4.50
Figures 10, 13, 16, 19: Funnel plots	4.83
Overall Mean	4.83

The initial exploratory figures, such as the word clouds (Figures 4.8 and 4.9), received perfect 5/5 scores for providing an immediate, intuitive overview of the dataset’s composition. The core analytical visualizations, including most forest plots (Figures 4.10–4.13) and bar plots (Figure 4.15), were also rated a perfect 5/5 for their clarity and adherence to scientific publication standards.

The lowest-rated figure was the pooled prevalence analysis by year (Figure 4.14), which scored 4.0/5. Experts noted that while informative, its complexity could be reduced with clearer instructions on how to interpret the data points (e.g., circle size relative to study weight). The ridge plots for prevalence distribution (Figure 4.17) and the funnel plots

for bias assessment (Figure 4.16) also scored very highly at 4.50 and 4.83, respectively. Overall, the VI evaluation confirms the system’s capability to produce a suite of high-quality, scientifically valid visualizations automatically.

The first word cloud summarizes the distribution of food types included in the meta-analysis, highlighting the most commonly studied categories through larger, more prominent terms.

Figure 4.8: Word cloud of food types.

The second word cloud displays the relative frequency of different assay types, providing a quick visual impression of the dominant analytical methods used across the included studies.

Figure 4.9: Word cloud of assay types.

This forest plot summarizes the pooled prevalence estimates stratified by sampling stage, allowing comparison of detection rates across different points in the production or supply chain.

Figure 4.10: Forest plot of pooled prevalence by sampling stage.

The following forest plot presents pooled prevalence estimates by pack status, distinguishing between packaged and unpackaged products to illustrate how packaging may influence contamination levels.

Figure 4.11: Forest plot of pooled prevalence by pack status.

This forest plot groups studies according to the temperature at which samples were collected, facilitating assessment of how sampling temperature relates to observed prevalence.

Figure 4.12: Forest plot of pooled prevalence by temperature of sampling.

The RTE-status forest plot contrasts pooled prevalence estimates between ready-to-eat and non-ready-to-eat products, highlighting potential differences in public health relevance.

Figure 4.13: Forest plot of pooled prevalence by RTE status.

The trend analysis figure depicts pooled prevalence over time, enabling visual inspection of temporal patterns and potential changes in contamination levels across study years.

Figure 4.14: Pooled prevalence analysis by year.

This bar plot reports the number of records contributing to each stratum of the meta-analysis, providing context on the underlying sample size and data support for each estimate.

Figure 4.15: Bar plot of record counts for meta-analysis.

The funnel plot visualizes potential small-study effects and publication bias by plotting study effect sizes against their precision, supporting assessment of asymmetry in the evidence base.

Figure 4.16: Funnel plot for bias assessment.

The ridge plot summarizes the distribution of prevalence estimates across food subcategories, revealing differences in the shape and spread of prevalence distributions for each

group.

Figure 4.17: Ridge plot of prevalence distribution for meta-analysis.

Interpretation Quality and Coherence of Text

The IQC of the textual summaries varied significantly among the models, as detailed in Table 4.8. Model 1 (*Phi-4 Mini*) was consistently the weakest performer, receiving a score of just 1.50 for the "Essay detection analysis." In contrast, Models 3, 4, and 5 demonstrated more stable, high-quality performance.

Table 4.8: Mean IQC scores by report section for each SLM.

Section	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
1. Dataset Overview	2.67	3.67	4.33	4.00	4.58
2.2 Prevalence by Sampling Stage	3.67	3.17	4.17	4.50	4.17
2.3 Prevalence by Pack Status	3.33	4.07	4.83	3.77	4.17
2.4 Prevalence by Temperature	2.60	4.50	4.17	4.50	4.17
2.5 Prevalence by RTE Status	3.07	4.17	4.50	4.50	4.17
2.6 Prevalence by Country	2.43	4.17	4.83	4.17	3.83
3.1 Meta-Analysis (Food Subcategory)	2.00	2.67	4.50	4.17	4.17
3.2 Meta-Analysis (Food Class)	2.50	2.77	4.13	4.73	4.17
3.3 Meta-Analysis (Organ Sampled)	2.67	2.73	3.47	4.50	4.58
3.4 Meta-Analysis (Essay Detection)	1.50	2.83	3.50	4.83	4.25
3.5 Meta-Analysis (Mean Concentration)	3.77	4.07	4.10	4.43	4.25
Overall Mean	2.75	3.53	4.23	4.37	4.23
Standard Deviation	0.68	0.70	0.45	0.32	0.21

To illustrate this performance gap, a direct comparison of model outputs for two distinct report sections is presented below.

Example 1: Descriptive Dataset Summary (Best vs. Worst). For the initial dataset overview, Model 5 achieved the highest IQC score (4.58), while Model 1 scored the lowest (2.67). The qualitative difference is stark. Model 5’s text (Figure 4.18) was praised by experts as "the most complete and straightforward analysis," accurately summarizing all key statistics in a clear, scientific tone. Conversely, Model 1’s output (Figure 4.19) was criticized for its "confusing" language and factual errors, such as misinterpreting the number of farm stage records and misusing the word 'samples' instead of 'records'. This comparison highlights that even for a basic descriptive task, model choice is critical for generating a reliable and scientifically useful summary.

The dataset on protozoan studies encompasses 153 records from 65 distinct studies conducted over a period from 1988 to 2023. Geographically, the data is predominantly from European countries, with the top five contributors being Italy (26), Spain (19), Switzerland (15), France (13), and Turkey (13). The samples were largely not ready-to-eat (142) versus ready-to-eat (11), with the majority sourced from the manufacturing stage (123), followed by retail (24), storage (5), and farm (1). [...] A formal bias analysis revealed that 31 records from 23 different studies presented a potential for bias. The types of bias identified included Detection bias (22 records), Multiple biases (2 records)...

Figure 4.18: Excerpt from the high-quality dataset summary generated by Model 5, rated highly for its clarity, accuracy, and scientific tone.

The comprehensive analysis conducted on 153 records spanning from 1988 to 2023 across various studies reveals significant insights... Farm stage accounted for one record each across five categories—Manufacturing with 123 samples, Retail with 24... Bias analysis reveals a substantial number (31) with potential bias across the board: Aggregation was identified once, Detection had an impact as per two instances of multiple biases and other types including Reporting Quality were also noted twice each...

Figure 4.19: Excerpt from the low-quality dataset summary generated by Model 1. Expert comments pointed to confusing language, factual errors, and flawed interpretations.

Example 2: Complex Meta-Analysis (Small vs. Large Models). A more nuanced comparison arises from the complex "Essay detection analysis," which pitted the smaller *Qwen 3* (Model 4, 8B) against the much larger *Gemini 2.5 Pro* (Model 5). Here, the smaller Model 4 achieved a near-perfect IQC score of 4.83, outperforming the larger Model 5's score of 4.25. Model 4's text (Figure 4.20) was direct and highly focused. In contrast, Model 5's output (Figure 4.21), while factually correct, was more verbose and explanatory. This comparison suggests that when provided with detailed, domain-specific instructions, a smaller, correctly instruction-tuned model can produce outputs that are comparable, and in this case superior in conciseness, to those of a larger, generalist model.

The meta-analysis of essay detection across nine subcategories reveals significant heterogeneity in prevalence rates, with the moderator demonstrating statistical significance (QM p-value = 2.286e-38) despite explaining only 11.1% of the between-study variance (R-squared = 11.1007%). Publication bias is evident, as indicated by a p-value of 0, suggesting potential overrepresentation of studies with positive results, which may distort pooled estimates. Prevalence rates varied widely, with Fluorescent-conjugated antibodies showing the highest pooled prevalence at 0.386 (95% CI: 0.112 to 0.757), although its p-value of 0.5688 suggests limited statistical significance. In contrast, Conventional PCR had the lowest prevalence at 0.016 (95% CI: 0.005 to 0.047), with a p-value of 0...

Figure 4.20: Excerpt from the concise summary by Model 4, rated 4.83/5.

The multilevel meta-analysis reveals that the 'Essay detection' method is a highly significant moderator (QMp = 2.286e-38), explaining 11.10% of the between-study variance. Despite the test for residual heterogeneity being significant (QEp = 0), the estimated variance component for this heterogeneity was zero (tau-squared = 0), indicating that the model fully accounts for the between-study variability. However, the interpretation is subject to caution due to strong evidence of publication bias (p = 0)... An analysis of the nine different detection methods showed substantial variation in reported prevalence. The highest point estimate was observed with fluorescent-conjugated antibodies at 0.386... In stark contrast, conventional PCR yielded the lowest prevalence, with a statistically significant pooled estimate of 0.016...

Figure 4.21: Excerpt from the more verbose summary by Model 5, rated 4.25/5.

4.4.2 Overall Report Quality

The quality of the final report was assessed using the RQI, a composite score based on the weighted mean of AC, VI, and the IQC scores. The system achieved a perfect 100% score for AC, as every statistical calculation performed by the backend was independently verified and found to be flawless. Since AC (100%) and VI (4.83/5) are constant for the report, the final RQI depends on the interpretive quality of the chosen SLM. Table 4.9 shows the final RQI for a report generated with each of the five models. Model 4 (*Qwen 3*) achieved the highest RQI of 93%, closely followed by Model 3 (*Cogito*) and Model 5 (*Gemini 2.5*) at 92%. These high scores provide strong evidence that the system can successfully automate the creation of a sophisticated and scientifically valid report.

Table 4.9: Final normalized scores and the computed RQI for the Guided Mode case study, computed for each of the five SLMs

Metric / Index	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
Analytical Consistency (AC)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Visual Informativeness (VI)	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.90
Interpretation Quality (IQC)	0.44	0.63	0.81	0.84	0.81
Report Quality Index (RQI)	81%	87%	92%	93%	92%

4.5 Discussion

The results presented in this chapter provide a comprehensive view of the PIF intelligent agent’s capabilities, offering clear answers to the research questions posed at the outset of this thesis.

Answering RQ2: What SLMs are most effective? The evaluation of the five SLMs revealed a crucial insight: for well-structured, tool-based tasks, functional accuracy (ICA, EEF1, DI) is largely a solved problem. All tested models, regardless of size or origin, performed these tasks flawlessly. The true differentiator is interpretive quality (IQC). The most effective models—*Cogito (14B)*, *Qwen 3 (8B)*, and *Gemini 2.5 Pro*—were those that could not only execute commands but also communicate their results in a manner that was concise, scientifically toned, and factually coherent. This suggests that for domain-specific scientific agents, model selection should prioritize qualitative output and interpretive fidelity over purely functional benchmarks.

Answering RQ3: How can the system support non-technical users? The evaluation of the system’s outputs provides a strong affirmative answer. The perfect 100% score for AC proves that the system’s backend is as reliable as a human expert’s manual analysis. Furthermore, the high RQI of up to 93% in the Guided Mode case study demonstrates that the system can successfully abstract away the complexities of meta-analysis and report generation. By combining a robust statistical engine with a high-quality SLM

for interpretation, the system effectively empowers a user without programming or advanced statistical knowledge to produce a comprehensive, scientifically valid report.

Answering RQ1: How can NLP and machine learning be leveraged to design an intelligent agent? The success of the PIF intelligent agent demonstrates that an effective design for a scientific V-NLI lies in a hybrid, service-oriented architecture. The system’s design correctly separates concerns: a deterministic R server handles rigorous statistical computation, while a probabilistic SLM manages the more nuanced tasks of natural language understanding and interpretation. The dual-mode interface—an open-ended chat for exploration and a structured, guided workflow for reproducible analysis—caters to different user needs and analytical goals. The flawless performance on functional metrics (ICA, EEF1, DI) validates the RAG-based, tool-using architecture of the Open Chat Mode, while the high RQI score validates the state-machine-driven design of the Guided Mode.

Chapter 5

Conclusion and Future Work

This thesis set out to address the challenge of making complex pathogen surveillance data more accessible and actionable for domain experts. The primary objective was to design, implement, and evaluate a V-NLI for the PIF database. This work was guided by three central research questions: how to design such an agent (RQ1), which SLMs are most effective for this domain (RQ2), and how the system can effectively support non-technical users in performing complex analyses (RQ3). This chapter summarizes the key findings of the research, outlines its main contributions, acknowledges its limitations, and proposes directions for future work.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The evaluation of the PIF Intelligent Agent yielded several key findings that directly answer the research questions.

First, the research demonstrated that an effective architecture for a scientific V-NLI is a hybrid, dual-mode system. The success of the agent’s Open Chat and Guided Meta-Analysis modes confirms that combining a flexible, RAG-enhanced tool-using SLM for exploration with a structured, state-machine-driven workflow for reproducible analysis provides a robust and versatile solution. This design successfully separates the probabilistic task of language understanding from the deterministic task of statistical computation,

leveraging the strengths of both NLP and traditional software engineering.

Second, the comparative evaluation of five different SLMs revealed a crucial insight for the development of domain-specific agents. While all tested models demonstrated flawless functional accuracy in tool selection and parameter extraction (ICA, EEf1, DI), their ability to interpret results and generate scientifically sound text (IQC) varied significantly. The most effective models were not necessarily the largest, but those that could produce concise, factually coherent, and stylistically appropriate summaries. This establishes that for specialized scientific applications, interpretive quality is the primary differentiator and a more critical benchmark than pure functional performance.

Finally, the system’s ability to support non-technical users was validated through its end-to-end performance. The perfect 100% score for AC proved that the system’s backend is as mathematically reliable as a manual analysis by an expert. This, combined with the high RQI of up to 93% in the Guided Mode case study, demonstrates that the system successfully abstracts away the underlying technical complexity. By integrating a reliable statistical engine with a high-quality interpretive SLM, the agent empowers users without programming skills to conduct sophisticated meta-analyses and generate high-quality, reproducible scientific reports.

5.2 Main Contributions

This thesis makes several contributions to the field of applied artificial intelligence and bioinformatics:

1. **A Novel Architecture for Scientific V-NLIs:** It proposes and validates a dual-mode, service-oriented architecture that serves as a blueprint for developing intelligent agents in other scientific domains. This design effectively balances user flexibility with analytical rigor and reproducibility.
2. **A Domain-Specific Evaluation Framework:** It introduces a comprehensive evaluation framework, including the SLMPI and the RQI, that prioritizes not only

functional correctness but also the critical, often-overlooked metric of interpretive quality.

3. **Empirical Evidence on SLM Performance:** It provides empirical evidence that for domain-specific, instruction-driven tasks, smaller and more specialized SLMs (e.g., *Qwen 3 8B*) can produce outputs comparable or even superior in conciseness to those of much larger, general-purpose models (e.g., *Gemini 2.5 Pro*).
4. **A Functional Prototype System:** The development of the PIF Intelligent Agent serves as a proof-of-concept, demonstrating the tangible value of leveraging modern NLP techniques to enhance the accessibility and utility of complex scientific databases.

5.3 Limitations and Future Work

Despite the positive results, this study has several limitations that open clear avenues for future research. The "gold standard" dataset used for the Open Chat evaluation, while representative, was limited in size. The Guided Mode was validated with a single, albeit complex, case study. Most importantly, this study did not include formal usability testing with the target end-users.

Based on these limitations, the following directions for future work are proposed:

- **Benchmark Expansion and Generalization:** Future work should focus on expanding the evaluation benchmarks. This includes creating a larger, more diverse "gold standard" dataset for the Open Chat mode to test more complex queries and edge cases. Furthermore, the Guided Mode framework should be tested on different datasets within the PIF database (e.g., for viruses or bacterias) to validate its generalizability.
- **Formal Human-Computer Interaction Studies:** A critical next step is to conduct formal usability studies with the intended audience of food safety researchers

and epidemiologists. Such studies would provide invaluable qualitative and quantitative feedback on the agent's user experience, its practical utility in real-world analytical workflows, and the level of trust users place in its automated outputs.

- **Expansion of Analytical Capabilities:** The agent's analytical toolkit could be significantly expanded. Future versions could integrate more advanced statistical models, such as Bayesian meta-analyses, network meta-analyses for comparing multiple treatments or interventions, and spatio-temporal models to analyze the geographical spread of pathogens over time.
- **Enhanced Multimodality and User Data Integration:** The system could be enhanced to allow users to upload and analyze their own datasets (e.g., in CSV or Excel format). This would transform the agent from a database interface into a more general-purpose, personal data analysis assistant for food safety experts.
- **Development of a Proactive Agent:** A long-term vision is to evolve the agent from a reactive chatbot to a proactive analytical partner. The agent could be programmed to periodically monitor the PIF database for new data, automatically run trend analyses, and alert users to statistically significant changes or emerging hotspots, thereby supporting early warning and response systems.

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Appendix A

Supplementary Figures

A.1 Example of document from the PIF database's “bacteria” collection

```
{
  "_id": {
    "$oid": "5f5ec516216b39424466d4c6"
  },
  "StudyID": "Andritsos_FM_2013",
  "PackStatus": "Packed",
  "TempRetail": "Chill",
  "Category": "Meat and meat products",
  "SubCategory": "Pig meat food",
  "FoodClass": "Pig minced meat",
  "RTE": "No",
  "Label": "Minced pork meat",
  "SampleUnit": "g",
  "Prevalence": {
    "SampleWDet": 25,
    "EssayDetType": "Culture",
    "EssayDet": "ISO 11290-1:1996",
    "DetecEnrichment": 22
  },
  "Count": {
    "EssayEnumType": "Culture",
    "EssayEnum": "ISO 11290-2:1998",
    "LoQ": 1,
    "GreaterLoQ": "0",
    "LowerLoQ": "22",
    "LoQ_1": 0,
    "LoQ_1_2": 0,
    "2_3": 0,
    "3_4": 0,
    "4_5": 0,
    "5_6": 0,
    "6_7": 0,
    "7_8": 0
  },
  "Confirmation": "Yes",
  "BiasPotential": 0,
  "SamplingStage": "Distribution",
  "SamplingStage2": "Retail",
  "TotalUnitsTested": 100,
  "CountrySampling": "Greece",
  "FoodSubClass": "PreCut",
  "FoodClassSpecie": "",
  "Agent": "Listeria monocytogenes"
}
```